

Case Study

Enhancing astronomy education for isolated Indigenous communities in Indonesia: A case study in Lampung

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The Lampung tribe is one of many Indigenous communities in Indonesia, residing in an isolated area far from Lampung Province's capital on Sumatra Island. Equitable access to education for children in such regions is essential for inclusive national development, as their isolation often means they lack access to information and educational facilities. This article presents a case study on introducing basic astronomy concepts to sixth-grade students living in an isolated area in Lampung Province. The project was initiated based on the researcher's observation of the lack of facilities in the elementary school of Gunung Katun Tanjungan village, occupied by the Lampung tribe. Additionally, it was noted that science instruction primarily relied on passive, lecture-based methods. In response, the researcher designed a project with two practical activities that require students to work together: a role-play and an exhibition gallery, to teach basic astronomy concepts. The result of these activities was that students became more enthusiastic about joining other science classes. As a notable outcome, one participating student qualified to compete in a regency-level science competition. Ultimately, this indicates that limited school facilities and living in an isolated area do not prevent students from earnestly engaging with scientific information.

Edited by

Yatny Yulianty and Muchammad Toyib

Reviewed by

Sisco Auala

Submitted 1 June 2024

Accepted 15 November 2025

Published 2 February 2026

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Citation

Wibowo, A.R.R. (2026). Enhancing astronomy education for isolated Indigenous communities in Indonesia: A case study in Lampung. *Communicating Astronomy with the Public Journal*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18452545>

1. Introduction

Indonesia comprises more than 17,000 islands, many of which are located in remote areas. These isolated areas are relatively poor, with limited access to development, economic benefits, and other public services such as education, health, technology, and communication. In Indonesia, such areas are categorised under the "3T" classification: terdapan (frontier), terluar (outermost), and tertinggal (disadvantaged). The Indonesian government has five guidelines for classifying specific locations as 3T. They include the border, economic conditions, human resources, development facilities and infrastructure, regional funding, access barriers, and the general characteristics of the territories ([Purwanda et al., 2023](#)).

One study identifies six causes that can make an area or a village disadvantaged, in addition to the five guidelines for classifying 3T areas mentioned by the Indonesian government. According to [Syamsuri \(2021\)](#), factors such as geographic isolation, limited infrastructure, weak human capital, natural resource constraints, disaster vulnerability, and policy neglect contribute to regional underdevelopment. Low levels of education exemplify Syamsuri's assertion of weak human capital in disadvantaged areas. Another related study noted that some of the education problems in 3T areas include the very low welfare and career levels of teachers serving in remote areas, lack of equitable distribution of education facilities, poor education services, difficult access to education, and limited distribution of qualified teachers in the 3T areas ([Luthfia et al., 2023](#)). Additionally, science education in these areas faces four specific challenges: unequal access to resources, low student performance, insufficient teacher training, and limited academic research and collaboration ([Faisal & Martin, 2019](#)).

The Tulang Bawang Barat Regency in Lampung province serves as an example of a typical 3T region, characterised by particularly pronounced educational disparities. Tulang Bawang Barat is a relatively new regency, established in 2009 ([Pemerintah Kabupaten Tulang Bawang Barat, 2025](#)). This regency is divided into nine subdistricts, each with several villages. This region is designated as disadvantaged because it is located in a remote area, and public transportation is scarce. Moreover, Tulang Bawang Barat Regency lacks education, health, and other resources because of its isolation from the province's capital city, and its economic development lags behind that of other regencies.

In the health sector, in 2014, Tulang Bawang Barat only had three hospitals, 11 community health centres, and nine drugstores. In the education sector, in 2016, this regency had only 175 elementary schools with 1,972 elementary school teachers, 50 junior high schools with 694 junior high school teachers, 14 senior high schools employing 309 senior high school teachers, and 18 vocational schools with 214 vocational school teachers. In Tulang Bawang Barat, the higher the school level, the fewer the number of schools and teachers that are available to the population of school-aged children and young adults ([Badan Pusat Statistik Kabupaten Tulang Bawang Barat, 2025](#)).

Lampung province has 15 regencies, and compared to Tulang Bawang Barat regency in 2016, three regencies had fewer elementary schools and elementary school teachers, three regencies had fewer junior high schools, two regencies had fewer junior high school teachers, two regencies had fewer senior high schools and senior high school teachers, four regencies had fewer vocational schools, and two regencies had fewer vocational school teachers ([Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Lampung, 2025](#)). These numbers indicate that in 2016, out of the 15 regencies in Lampung province, Tulang Bawang Barat ranked low in the education sector, though not at the very bottom. Moreover, this demonstrates that education quality in the whole of Lampung province was not equal. Compared to other provinces in Indonesia, particularly those on Java Island, where the capital is located, a larger gap is revealed.

In response to these regional disparities, the Indonesian government has launched several initiatives to improve educational equity in the 3T regions. The Ministry of Education and Culture has launched the Sarjana Mendidik di Daerah Terdepan, Terluar, Tertinggal (SM3T) initiative, a programme aimed at giving bachelor of education graduates a chance to participate in accelerating educational development in 3T areas for one year. The programme is designed to prepare professional educators to overcome the shortage of educator resources, especially in 3T areas.

In addition to government efforts, society has also initiated programmes to improve education in the 3T areas. One of them is Indonesia Mengajar, a programme to empower the nation's brightest young people. They are recruited, trained, and deployed to serve their communities as teachers in remote areas of Indonesia for one year. Indonesia Mengajar programme stays in every assignment area for five years, so it recruits and sends different people as teachers to an assignment area every year. After five years, Indonesia Mengajar leaves the assignment area so that the community can grow, meaning that after five years, the assignment area can continue its efforts to advance education in its region independently without the Indonesia Mengajar teachers. Tulang Bawang Barat Regency hosted Indonesia Mengajar from 2010 to 2014, before initiating Tulang Bawang Barat Cerdas, the continuation of the Indonesia Mengajar programme.

Aside from the fact that Tulang Bawang Barat is geographically isolated, the Lampung tribe's standard of living is, on average, lower than that of immigrant tribes such as the Javanese. In the Tulang Bawang Barat regency, there are local Lampung and immigrant tribes. The majority of the Lampung tribe lives in old settlements, known locally as *tiyuh tuho*, and the immigrant tribes live in villages designated as *Kampung Bali*, *Kampung Jawa*, and other *kampung*s. Due to the disparity between the Lampung tribe and the immigrant tribes, such as Javanese and Balinese, the regency government of Tulang Bawang Barat initiated a similar programme to Indonesia Mengajar after it concluded its work in 2014. The regent of Tulang Bawang Barat and other related stakeholders first discussed this programme, known as Tulang Bawang Barat Cerdas, in 2014. The focus of the Tulang Bawang Barat Cerdas is to continue Indonesia Mengajar's efforts to create better educational opportunities in the regency, particularly in the old villages of the Lampung tribe.

The first cohort of education facilitators, 12 educators in all, of the Tulang Bawang Barat Cerdas programme was placed in 12 of the regency's villages in December 2015. These educators lived with the locals and taught in the village's primary school for one year. In addition to their educational goals, the facilitators of the Tulang Bawang Barat Cerdas programme aimed to inspire children and communities to create equitable educational opportunities and build a community that is aware of and involved in the advancement of education.

One of the old settlements, Gunung Katun Tanjungan, is considerably disadvantaged. This village is far inland, isolated and small, with few natural resources. It is surrounded by a large

rubber forest, which is the village's primary source of income, and close to a river, where some locals collect fish for profit. The only school in Gunung Katun Tanjungan is the public elementary school, so students are forced to continue their education in subdistricts or regencies that have a more developed educational infrastructure. However, this can be prohibitive. If a family cannot afford to send their child to one of these nearby schools, the students will likely begin working at a young age to help support the community. Similarly, the village is host to a small community health centre that cannot accommodate medical emergencies, and so villagers must travel to nearby subdistricts to receive medical care. The village is further isolated by its inconsistent and poor telecommunications connection: the signal is only available at certain locations. This general lack of infrastructure in Gunung Katun Tanjungan significantly disadvantages residents from having access to the fundamental resources needed for knowledge and capacity building and community development.

The educational challenges in remote, underdeveloped, and outermost (3T) regions are exacerbated by insufficient infrastructure and geographical isolation. Academic research identifies multiple issues in these areas, including the limited career prospects and low welfare of educators, a lack of equitable educational facilities, substandard educational services, difficult access to schooling, and an uneven distribution of qualified teaching staff. Corresponding studies propose several viable solutions, such as adopting a context-sensitive approach that understands local conditions, fostering partnerships with communities, and incorporating indigenous culture into the curriculum. Further recommendations include the development of relevant learning resources and the implementation of project-based learning. Moreover, the digital transformation of education and the provision of adequate infrastructure are critical components for improvement. Initiatives like the Guru Mengabdi programme contribute significantly by enhancing teacher quality and reinforcing the curriculum. Ultimately, expanding educational access in 3T regions necessitates collaboration between government, community, and the private sector via public-private partnerships, alongside scholarship programmes and targeted educational assistance ([Luthfia et al., 2023](#); [Dalimunthe et al., 2025](#)).

Within the Indonesian educational context, local cultural elements have been incorporated into several formal subjects, including Civic Education, Social Science, Muatan Lokal, character education, Islamic Religious Education, Bahasa Indonesia, and English ([Saleh et al., 2023](#); [Sumarni et al., 2024](#); [Umam & Husain, 2024](#); [Wibowo, 2024](#); [Wulandari et al., 2024](#)). The cultural content integrated into the national curriculum typically encompasses themes such as food, systems of production, traditional medicine, housing, clothing, and social organisation ([Badriah & Sukati, 2021](#)). Concurrently, research into science pedagogy indicates that integrating local culture can foster a more profound and contextually relevant learning experience. This approach also supports cultural preservation, strengthens student identity, instils an appreciation for local heritage, and enhances scientific literacy ([Rini, 2023](#); [Putra & Wahyuni, 2025](#); [Widiarini et al., 2025](#)). Illustrative examples include the use of the bundengan—a traditional Wonosobo musical instrument that produces gamelan-like sounds—to teach the physics of waves and

sound, and the application of the mattojang tradition, a customary swinging game in Bugis culture, to elucidate the concept of vibration in physics lessons ([Rahayu et al., 2022](#); [Rika et al., 2025](#)).

Collectively, these studies highlight a research gap concerning the integration of Indigenous knowledge into formal astronomy education within Indonesia. A principal factor contributing to this lacuna is the absence of a dedicated Astronomy subject in the national curriculum; instead, astronomical concepts are incorporated into other disciplines, such as elementary-level science. This article aims to contribute to the existing scholarship on cultural integration in formal science education by focusing specifically on astronomy-related topics. While Indonesia may lack case studies on this particular issue within a formal astronomy subject, numerous international examples exist. For instance, [Lee et al. \(2020\)](#) advocate for the inclusion of indigenous astronomical knowledge in museum and planetarium settings to provide visitors with cross-cultural experiences. Presenting celestial narratives that elucidate how past societies lived and what they believed can foster an awareness that these stories are not merely myths, but rather functioned as guiding frameworks for ancient civilisations.

Research into formal education in Canada indicates that the authentic integration of indigenous knowledge can manifest in multiple forms. These include presenting indigenous astronomical concepts and terminology as equally valid to Western scientific knowledge, and facilitating student understanding of the interconnectedness of knowledge and the significance of relationships within scientific study ([O'Shea et al., 2021](#)). A parallel example from Australia demonstrates that educational outcomes can be enhanced when indigenous knowledge systems are afforded the space to coexist with the dominant paradigm of Western science. The introduction of cultural sky narratives into the science curriculum engaged year 5 and 6 pupils, motivating them to seek further sky stories and explore the astronomical content aligned with the national science curriculum. This initiative was significantly enriched by the involvement of Aboriginal elders and community members, creating a more profound learning experience for all participants ([Ruddell et al., 2016](#)).

In line with the work of [Ruddell et al. \(2016\)](#), this article presents a case study of an astronomy-themed educational initiative conducted in Gunung Katun Tanjungan village. The project was undertaken in 2016, during the researcher's assignment as an education facilitator for the Tulang Bawang Barat Cerdas programme. While the Indonesian elementary school curriculum does not include astronomy as a distinct subject, basic astronomical content is introduced in the 6th-grade science syllabus, particularly through a unit on the solar system. This unit marks students' first formal engagement with astronomical concepts, including the identification of celestial bodies, the rotation and revolution of planets, solar and lunar eclipses, and the use of the Gregorian and Hijri calendars. The project was designed to explore strategies for effectively introducing fundamental astronomy concepts in a rural, under-resourced educational setting, with the broader aim of enhancing astronomy communication among young learners in disadvantaged areas.

2. Method

The project commenced in December 2015, when the facilitator (hereafter referred to as the researcher) was deployed to Gunung Katun Tanjungan village as part of the Tulang Bawang Barat Cerdas initiative. In Indonesia, the academic year starts in July and ends in June of the next year. So, when the researcher arrived at the village, the school had started its semester break. From mid-December 2015 until 1 January 2016, the researcher had about two weeks to observe the situation in the village and the school. She engaged informally with residents to build rapport and gain contextual understanding of the village culture.

This study adopted a qualitative, single-case participatory approach, guided by action research principles. Single-case participatory approach was chosen because the researcher was placed by the Tulang Bawang Barat Cerdas in one school for a year. She could not teach and create projects in other schools. Moreover, she did not have any best practices examples on communicating astronomy science from previous research in Indonesia. So, she created the project based on her observation of the daily teaching and learning process at the Gunung Katun Tanjungan elementary school.

Data were collected through field observations, participant interactions, and informal reflection conversations. Initial observations indicated that local educators predominantly employ lecture-based instruction, requiring students to passively record and memorise content, with minimal integration of practical activities in science classes. To address this pedagogical limitation, the researcher designed an intervention centred on active student engagement. This decision was informed by evidence suggesting that while the lecture method can be effective when used in isolation, its efficacy is significantly enhanced when combined with instructional strategies targeting higher-order cognitive skills ([Akpan & Nkan, 2022](#)). In collaborative learning environments, the instructor assumes the role of a facilitator, offering guidance and prompts to stimulate active participation.

[Laal & Ghodsi \(2012\)](#) defined collaborative learning as a group-oriented methodology emphasising problem-solving, task execution, and knowledge construction. This approach yields multiple benefits, including improved academic performance, enhanced productivity, and the development of supportive interpersonal dynamics. Notably, collaborative learning aligns with the cultural values of the Lampung community, which emphasises mutual assistance and collective effort through the principle of Sakai Sambatan, a tradition rooted in cooperation and communal solidarity ([Saputri & Sudirman, 2024](#)).

Recognising the pedagogical advantages of collaboration and its cultural resonance, the researcher implemented two interactive activities—role-playing and an exhibition gallery—within an astronomy education context. These activities were structured to leverage peer learning, kinaesthetic engagement, and artistic expression, all of which have been shown to enhance comprehension and retention in science education ([Henriksen, 2014](#); [Liliawati et al., 2018](#); [Keerthirathne, 2020](#)). Due to scheduling constraints, each activity was conducted over

a single 90-minute session, divided into two 45-minute segments, ensuring alignment with standard class durations.

2.1 Project Preparation

The researcher recognised that securing the trust of the indigenous community was essential for the successful implementation of the Tulang Bawang Barat Cerdas programme, as the initiative's feasibility hinged upon establishing credibility with local stakeholders. This observation aligns with prior research indicating that rural communities often exhibit scepticism toward outsiders, place a high value on traditional customs and social etiquette, maintain strong familial and communal bonds, communicate directly, and display initial reticence when interacting with unfamiliar individuals ([Syamsuri, 2021](#)). Additionally, such communities emphasise reciprocity, demonstrating respect and gratitude toward those who extend goodwill.

To foster trust, the researcher engaged in sustained community involvement, including participation in cultural ceremonies, informal dialogues with residents, and supplementary educational support. These efforts commenced upon the researcher's arrival in the village and continued throughout the second academic semester (beginning 2 January 2016) until the conclusion of the researcher's assignment period in December 2016. Given the village's compact size—permeable within a single day—the researcher determined that regular, face-to-face interactions with community members were the most effective means of establishing rapport.

Through sustained engagement, the researcher identified key community leaders whose endorsement was critical for programme advocacy. Furthermore, immersion in the local sociocultural context facilitated proficiency in the indigenous language, a factor known to enhance researcher credibility and ensure methodological rigor in cross-cultural studies ([Pelzang & Hutchinson, 2018](#)).

2.2 Project Implementation

The study targeted sixth-grade students, as astronomy-related content is integrated into their science curriculum. At the time of implementation, the class consisted of 12 students. The project employed two primary instructional activities: (1) a role-play exercise to demonstrate planetary rotation and revolution, and (2) an exhibition gallery to explore solar eclipses, lunar eclipses, and the Gregorian and Hijri calendars. Table 1 below summarises the two activities initiated by the researcher.

	Role play	Exhibition gallery
Learning objectives	Students understood celestial movements.	Students understood solar eclipses, lunar eclipses, and the Gregorian and Hijri calendars.
Student role	Role-playing celestial objects: 1 student played the Sun, 1 student played 9 planets, and 1 student played the Moon.	Presenting a poster and visiting others' galleries to listen to other presentations.
Materials	N/A	Paper, pencils, colouring pencils, and glue.
Indicators of engagement	Students did their role and practiced rotation and revolution.	Students presented their galleries, asked, and answered questions.

Table 1 Learning activities

The intervention began with an introductory session on celestial bodies to activate students' prior knowledge. This was followed by an embodied learning activity in which students engaged in role-play to simulate planetary motion. Each student selected a celestial body to represent (e.g., the Sun, Mercury, Venus, Earth, or other solar system planets). Once roles were assigned, students physically enacted the rotation (spinning on their axes) and revolution (orbiting around the student representing the Sun). One student assumed the role of the Moon, demonstrating its rotation and revolution around the Earth. This kinaesthetic approach facilitated active participation, peer interaction, and an engaging learning environment. A post-activity discussion allowed students to reflect on their experiences and articulate key takeaways regarding planetary dynamics.

The second activity involved a collaborative project on solar eclipses, lunar eclipses, and calendar systems, structured as an exhibition gallery. The 12 students were divided into four groups of three members each. Through a lottery system, each group was assigned a specific topic to present. Before the exhibition, groups designed educational posters, incorporating creative elements to enhance visual appeal and effectively communicate their assigned concepts. Once completed, the posters were displayed on the classroom walls.

The exhibition procedure was as follows: each group selected one representative to visit other galleries while the remaining two members presented their poster to visiting peers. A 15-minute preparation period allowed groups to assign roles and rehearse their explanations. Following the gallery walk, a structured debriefing session provided students with an opportunity to share

insights gained from both presenting and engaging with their peers' work. This multimodal approach—combining embodied learning and collaborative exhibition—enhanced student engagement and reinforced astronomical concepts through active participation and peer-mediated instruction.

2.3 Project Evaluation

The evaluation was conducted after each activity in the form of a structured sharing session. During these sessions, students were allotted time to freely express their reflections, sharing their feelings, opinions, and key learning takeaways. The students exhibited significant interest and enthusiasm upon their initial exposure to the project-based learning approach, as they had no prior experience with such methods. Traditionally, instruction in their science classes had been predominantly lecture-based, requiring passive note-taking and textbook memorisation. Consequently, the introduction of interactive elements—such as role-playing and exhibition gallery presentations—elicited marked excitement. This heightened engagement was evident in their expressive demeanour and active participation.

Students perceived the learning activities as dynamic and less formal, which contributed to reduced anxiety and increased motivation. However, given their unfamiliarity with student-centred pedagogical approaches, an adjustment period was necessary. During the role-playing segment, for instance, some students initially struggled to adapt; despite prior explanations, they remained uncertain and treated the activity with a degree of levity. The adaptation process became more observable during the preparation phase for the exhibition gallery. Students relied heavily on rote memorisation, meticulously transcribing and rehearsing their explanations rather than engaging in more creative or spontaneous presentations. Consequently, during the actual exhibition, many read directly from their notes instead of delivering more extemporaneous or interactive explanations of their posters. The prompt questions that the researchers asked the students to evaluate what they got from the two activities are listed below:

1. Tell me and your friends your feelings after conducting the activities.
2. What did you do to prepare yourself before the activities?
3. What challenges or difficulties did you find during the activities?
4. What have you learned from the activities?

The project was conducted in March 2016, aligning with the science curriculum for sixth-grade students, which designates the solar system as the final topic of the academic year. Over a two-month observation period, the researcher examined local teaching methods through classroom observations and student accounts. Findings revealed that instruction predominantly relied on rote memorisation and note-taking across all subjects, including science, despite the potential for more engaging and creative pedagogical approaches. In response, the researcher developed innovative methods to teach celestial phenomena, emphasising experiential and collaborative learning.

Given that astronomical objects cannot be physically observed or manipulated by students, role-play and an exhibition gallery were implemented as effective strategies. Role-playing allowed students to kinaesthetically enact planetary motions, fostering embodied cognition—a method supported by [Henriksen \(2014\)](#), who documented the use of theatre and movement in science education to enhance conceptual understanding. Additionally, the exhibition gallery facilitated peer learning, where students explained concepts to one another in an interactive setting. This approach aligns with the findings in [Keerthirathne \(2020\)](#) that peer-mediated learning reduces teacher-centred pressure and promotes a more relaxed, student-driven educational environment.

The astronomy lessons incorporated culturally relevant examples, such as planetary rotation and revolution, eclipses, and the Gregorian and Hijri calendars. Students recognised connections between these concepts and their local practices. For instance, the traditional bawang fishing method in Lampung relies on tidal patterns ([Nurdin & Ng, 2013](#)), which students explored through role-playing Earth's movements. This application of household funds of knowledge ([Moll et al., 1992](#)) demonstrates how integrating cultural context can enhance science education.

Furthermore, the study highlighted the intersection of astronomy and religious practices in the predominantly Muslim community of Gunung Katun Tanjungan. The Hijri calendar, based on lunar cycles, governs Islamic observances such as Ramadan and Eid Al Fitr. Through role-play and the exhibition gallery, students engaged with lunar revolution concepts, deepening their understanding of the link between scientific principles and daily life. However, while students demonstrated awareness of these connections, parental input and home observations were not included to verify the external application of these concepts.

3. After-Project Learning Points

The project yielded three primary insights: the importance of trust-building in indigenous education contexts, the value of connecting science with local culture, and the adaptability of creative pedagogy in resource-limited environments.

The success of a research project is often contingent on the trust established with the community involved. This was particularly critical when working with the Lampung people, who had limited prior interaction with external researchers. Their initial wariness, as noted by [Syamsuri \(2021\)](#), is common in rural communities that may exhibit suspicion toward strangers. To overcome this barrier, the researcher prioritised sustained communication and invested significant time in learning the local language. This commitment was fundamental in building rapport and moving beyond initial hesitations.

Cultivating trust required key interpersonal skills: cultural sensitivity, linguistic adaptability,

and empathetic communication. The dedicated four-month effort to learn the Lampung language demonstrated a genuine commitment to meaningful engagement. Furthermore, strategic communication was essential; interactions were tailored to different stakeholders. Discussions with schoolteachers focused on educational subjects, while conversations with village leaders centred on local development and prosperity. This nuanced approach facilitated smoother interactions and deeper community engagement.

A central learning objective was to connect astronomy with local traditions and religious practices. The researcher achieved this by immersing herself in local ceremonies and daily life, gaining firsthand insight into Lampung cultural values. This immersion allowed for the identification of natural connections, such as linking astronomical phenomena to the bawang fishing method and the timing of the Ramadan and Eid al-Fitr celebrations. By grounding scientific concepts in culturally relevant contexts, the research enhanced its accessibility and significance for the community.

Finally, designing an effective outreach project required a needs-based approach, tailored to an isolated area with significant limitations. In Gunung Katun Tanjungan village, limited infrastructure and a remote location restricted access to contemporary scientific knowledge. The prevalence of conventional, lecture-based teaching methods further highlighted the urgent need for innovative, engaging pedagogical strategies to make astronomy relevant and accessible.

In designing the creative teaching methods, the researcher utilised two things: the local culture and the students' ability to explain the materials to their friends. As explained in the project evaluation above, the local culture being used is the traditional fishing method named bawang and the religious practice, namely fasting during the Ramadan season and Eid Al Fitr celebration.

Leveraging local traditions, such as the bawang fishing method and Ramadan-related astronomical observations, helped contextualise scientific concepts. Research supports the effectiveness of integrating arts and culture into STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education ([Liliawati et al., 2018](#)). This project employed performance-based learning (role-play) and visual communication (gallery exhibitions) to enhance engagement and comprehension.

The gallery exhibition activity encouraged collaborative learning, where students explained concepts to their peers. Peer learning has been shown to improve educational outcomes by fostering a supportive and low-pressure environment ([Liu & Chen, 2020](#)). Observations confirmed that this method increased student enthusiasm and participation, with one student advancing to a regency-level science competition—demonstrating the potential of culturally responsive science education in marginalised (3T) regions.

4. Conclusions

This case study demonstrates that geographic isolation and infrastructural constraints do not inherently impede students' access to science education when innovative, context-responsive pedagogical strategies are implemented. Effective astronomy instruction in such settings requires knowledge, creativity, and innovative approaches to engage students. The distinguishing feature of this project was its methodology for teaching fundamental astronomy concepts. Traditional science instruction in comparable contexts often emphasises rote memorisation and passive learning, with minimal integration of hands-on or inquiry-based activities. In this study, the researcher employed role-playing and an exhibition gallery to foster student creativity and active participation.

Post-activity reflections indicated enhanced student engagement and reduced learning anxiety, with participants expressing positive emotional responses and enthusiastic involvement during discussion sessions. Notably, students retained their posters as keepsakes, displaying them on classroom walls after lessons. The project also heightened students' curiosity toward other science topics, leading to increased participation in science classes. A significant outcome was the involvement of a sixth-grade student in a regency-level science competition—a notable achievement, as it marked the first participation of a student from Gunung Katun Tanjungan Elementary School in such an event alongside peers from across Tulang Bawang Barat Regency, including schools outside the old villages' region.

The findings suggest that this case study can serve as a replicable model for other underserved (3T) regions in Indonesia. Key takeaways include the value of incorporating local cultural elements and employing creative methodologies in astronomy and broader science education. This approach highlights the potential for adaptable, student-centred strategies to overcome educational barriers in resource-limited settings.

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